

Teachers and School Administrators' Perception on the Use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool

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Abstract:- This study aimed determine the perception of the teachers' and school administrators on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. This study used descriptive-correlation design with qualitative support in gathering the data. Complete enumeration in choosing the teachers and school administrators was done, however only thirty school administrators and eighty-nine for the teachers responded the questionnaire. An adopted and modified questionnaire using parallelism technique on the perception of teachers and school administrators was used which was gathered through a survey using Google forms sent via messenger apps to the teachers and school administrators of Sultan Naga Dimaporo, Lanao del Norte. Validity and reliability test of the questionnaire was done beforehand. PSP software and MS 365 were used to analyze the data. Based on the factor analysis, teachers' and school administrators' perception was classified into clarity of purpose and usefulness in the teaching and learning process. Results revealed teachers and school administrators both have a high positive perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose, meanwhile a positive perception in terms of its usefulness in the teaching and learning process. Consequently, a no significant difference was found between teachers and school administrators' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in the teaching and learning process. Moreover, students' ability to understand and have positive engagement in learning, difficulty in achieving objectives and positive learning outcomes, lack of awareness in the indicators, insufficient instructional materials, observer's preferences, preparation, and the nature of the tool were the challenges identified by the teachers and school administrators. To cope with the mentioned challenges the following strategies were both used by the teachers and school administrators, such as time management, peer tutoring, giving more technical assistance, constant communication, self-learning, intensive training, and workshop specifically on the use of ICT. The study concluded that the standardized classroom observation tool had empower them to reflect on their own teaching and supervising and identify pedagogical needs and initiate innovation for the benefit of the learners. It is highly recommended that teachers and school administrators discuss issues about required standards in the performance of duties and be updated on what is

required of them by making this as one of the topics during learning action cell sessions and in-service training

Keywords:- Perception, School Administrators, Teachers, Classroom Observation Tool

I. INTRODUCTION

Classroom observations are integral part in the teaching process. This is done throughout a teacher's career which is either part of the supervision and/or monitoring of the school administrators. Giving a positive critical framework for evaluating one's practice, improving skills, and developing strengths can be considered as necessity for conducting classroom observation. However, conducting classroom observation can create stress and test confidence of the one being observed.

According to Lopez (2016), teaching excellence is not genetically endowed power but a result of rigorous and inspired performance. Thus, using an appropriate instructional tool makes teacher efficient and effective. Learning what materials to be used and of teaching to use them comes with experience. Moreover, one of the most important roles that teachers play is that of a classroom manager. Effective teaching and learning cannot take place in a poorly managed classroom. It is very important to take note that a well-managed classroom provides an environment in which teaching, and learning can flourish. But a well-managed classroom does not just come out from nowhere. It takes a good deal of effort to create that conducive classroom climate (Corpuz and Salandanan, 2015).

Consequently, in the Philippines, the Republic Act 10533 also known as K to 12 Law, features that classroom observation as one measure in ensuring quality teaching. Section 14 of the law indicates that the Department of Education (DepEd) will report on different aspects needed in the implementation that includes teacher welfare and training needs which may be measured via teacher classroom observation. Feedback provides quality input for the continuous improvement and provides opportunities to share ideas and expertise (Department of Education, 2017).

The DepEd officials noted that the classroom observation mandated in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS) has "become more

objective and standardized, and is used for mentoring, coaching, performance review and evaluation which supports the teachers' on-going professional development" (Dela Cruz, 2019). Classroom observation was defined as a process of providing feedback to a teacher's classroom practice.

It also encourages teachers to reflect and develop self-awareness about their practice and provides evidence of an actual teacher performance, their strengths, and areas of improvement (Revised Results-Based Performance Management System Manual, 2018). Riego de Dios (2020) stated that the respondents reported that all the indicators are about work values are important. To assess classroom practices, in as much as to identify the strengths and areas that needs to be improved, a classroom observation tool has been developed based on the new set of professional standards. This is to accurately come up with professional development programs, targeted at the specific needs of teachers. Asio and Jimenez (2020) disclosed the context of professional development and the majority of the employees who took part in the survey agreed.

Moreover, it was reiterated by the Department of Education the need to conduct of all on-going class observations to help ensure the delivery of quality basic education to all learners under its care. The DepEd recognizes that teachers play a crucial role in upgrading the quality of teaching and learning process. Hence, through classroom observation, teacher's performance can be improved through different parameters in achieving quality education.

Thus, this study aimed to determine the teachers' and school administrators' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Based on the findings of this study, school administrators can benefit from doing an efficient, timely, and significant observation of teachers.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

School administrators and teachers are being retrained and retooled to support school's adoption to new trend in the 21st century education. Changes specifically in the delivery of quality education impacts teacher's competency and performance standards. According to Department of Education (2015), corporate objectives and performance evaluation should be linked. Indicators are critical for monitoring individual performance and its effect on company goals.

Typically, teachers in our country are the key for the improvement of our educational system. They are considered vital to raising student achievement (Results-Based Performance Management System Manual, 2018). Therefore, it is very important to have a good educational system on our country because they are the one to make difference in the teaching and learning process.

In line with this, DepEd classroom observation in the new normal uses an instrument called the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) with nine indicators: 1.) "Apply

knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas." 2.) Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills". 3.) Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills". 4.) Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments ". 5.) Manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments ". 6.) Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences". 7.) Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts". 8.) "Select, develop, organize and use appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals." 9.) Designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements." The COT is an interactive platform that gives vital highlights and does not require complex inferences or judgments made by an observer. It is highly objective and specific and can be used to code observed behavior easily.

There are two Classroom Observation Tools for RPMS (COT-RPMS), one for Teachers I-III (RPMS), one for Teachers I-III (Proficient) and one for Master Teachers I-IV (Highly Proficient). The indicators in the tools are the observable classroom objectives listed in the RPMS tools. The language of the indicators is from the Proficient career stage in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teacher (PPST). COT-RPMS for Teachers I-III has nine (9) indicators, while the COT-RPMS for Master Teacher I-IV has five (5) indicators (RPMS Manual, 2018). Also, the classroom observation has pre-determined indicators that have been agreed upon by the teachers themselves and the observers, ensuring the teachers' preparedness. In a related study, an effective supervision process consists of steps of pre-observation planning, observation implementation, and post-observation monitoring (Ghavifekr, Husain, Rosden and Hamat, 2019).

To make teaching and learning more visible, classroom observation plays a central role. It provides teachers with constructive critical feedback to improve their classroom management and instructional techniques. Furthermore, school administrators employ evaluation techniques that serve multiple purposes, such as, to provide summative scores for accountability purposes, inform decisions about tenure or dismissal, identify teachers in need of remediation, or provide formative feedback to improve teacher's practice (Little, Goe and Bell, 2009). Observations are considered as the most direct way to measure teaching practice because the evaluator can see the full dynamics of the classroom.

As mandated in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS). It also became more objective and standardized. This is so since it is used for mentoring,

coaching, performance review, and evaluation. As added by Suparto (2020), quality of teacher learning can be improved with classroom observation techniques.

Moreover, as mentioned by the Department of Education, the standardized classroom observation has predetermined indicators that have been agreed upon by the teachers themselves and the observers, ensuring the teachers' preparedness as they know exactly what to prepare and what teaching behaviors are expected from them in the observation (Dela Cruz, 2019).

In the study conducted by Barrogo (2020), standardized classroom observation tool serves as a guide for the teachers to assess their performance and plan for their improvement, thus, enhancement of teachers' preparation and competency. Furthermore, Barrogo concluded, that the standardized classroom observation tool was made not to add burden to our teachers but to help them in planning their teaching-learning process and other phases included in the profession.

Hence, classroom observation tool (COT) is required for every teacher in the Public Schools to test the teacher's capacity and method of teaching. It is mandatory by the Department of Education to go on this process four times every School Year. Typically, the critics is the Master teacher or principal and administrator of the school. Scores given will help teachers and will give them room for improvements.

With the aim of the professional development, classroom observation tool would empower teachers to reflect on their own teaching and identify pedagogical needs and initiate innovation for the benefit of the learners. One of the features in using the classroom observation tool (COT) as it allows teacher and school administrator to conduct a pre-observation conference and a post-observation conference. During pre-observation conference the teacher and the evaluator have time to discuss the lesson, engage in collaborative decision making, clarify what is to be expected by the rater to ratee and identify areas where feedback will be provided. Furthermore, during the post-observation conference, classroom observation tool builds a strong relationship between the teachers and the school administrators/principals for it can provide them a meaningful moment in which they can talk freely in a positive way resulting in a sympathetic and trusting bond (Barrogo, 2020). Dizon, San Pedro, Munsayac, Padilla, and Pascual (2018) mentioned that DepEd strengthens its performance and responsibility culture while adhering to its overall organizational directive, vision, and mission by adopting the RPMS as its Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS).

III. REVIEW OF RELATED STUDY

One of the most common forms of teacher evaluation is school administrators or principals' classroom observations (Brandt et al., 2007). A classroom observation is a formal or informal observation of teaching that takes place in a classroom or other learning environment (Dela Cruz, 2019). Consequently, classroom observations are the most common

form of teacher evaluation and vary widely in how they are conducted and what evaluate. Generally, this can be conducted by school administrators/principals, fellow teacher administrators or instructional specialists that used to provide teachers with positive and constructive critical feedback aimed at improving teachers' classroom management and instructional techniques. Indeed, school administrators must then regularly observe teachers as an extension of career-performance evaluations.

For teachers it is important to observe the interaction between teacher-learner within the classroom because it can determine the learning opportunities that students get. Not only that, but classroom observation also encourages colleagues to collaborate to improve teacher practice and student learning. Feedback from classroom observations is an effective way for providing teachers with the information they need about their classroom behavior (Halim, Wahid and Halim, 2020).

Yusrina and Bima (2020), added that observation of teacher practice may provide information on whether learning takes place in the classroom. Hence, enhancing teacher quality ranks foremost in the many educational reform efforts towards quality education. If the learning of the teacher stagnant on the everyday lives, they will not prosper and they will not learn from new techniques of the teaching strategies. It is obvious that in this modern world, we can see the teaching method is growing fast, and the modern technology is growing fast so, in this case the teaching method must also be in line with this modern technology.

A classroom observation is an act of watching a teacher's performance in their classroom or leaning environment. Classroom observations are a quantitative way of recording and measuring teacher behavior and mastery by systematically watching and recording them in action (Torsh, 2019). Classroom observation is purposively done to improve the students' outcomes by improving the instructional prowess of the teacher.

Classroom observation is a critical component of the RMPS because it delivers instructions and assesses learners' behavior. As the term suggests, learners observe behaviors and events recorded (Impoff, 2020). It employs various instruments to facilitate the effective collection of data. Some of the tools are also used in research, and they may include classroom observation schedules and stalling observation schedules. Through these instruments, educators can stimulate change and gather more valuable information while providing clear evidence and collecting data from naturalistic education settings. Accordingly, this improves education and enhances understanding. A classroom teacher invites a master teacher, head teacher, or the school head into their classroom to observe. Whether they are master teachers or beginning teachers, all the teachers involved could dialogue together and learn through a post-conference (Caratiquit and Pablo, 2021).

Moreover, Wairimu (2016), investigated teachers’ perceptions of head teachers’ classroom observation practices in Nakuru district government elementary schools. Results revealed that teachers agreed that instructional supervision enhances teaching and learning and that head teachers manage classrooms, which they viewed positively.

In our daily lives we always evaluate everything we come into contact with. As you can observe on the COT (Class Observation Tool) of every teacher on Public Schools it is required on every teacher to go on that process four times every school year to test the capacity and method of teaching of Public-School teacher. It is mandatory by Department of Education. Normally the critics is the Master teacher at every school or Principals and Administrator of the school, and the latter will not perfect your score because there is always room for improvement. To improve more on your teaching and to have more opportunities to become more effective and efficient Public School Teacher. Because the teacher in our country is the key for the improvement of our educational system. In literature there are studies about teachers; perception on the use of classroom observation tool, however none of this dealt with the perception of the school administrators on the use of the tool. Much more in comparing by looking the difference between the perception of the

IV. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The following theories, Classroom Observation Theory, Constructivism theory of Piaget, and Urie Bronfenbrenner Bio-ecological Systems Theory, had supported this study.

Given this study, that focus on classroom observation and its perceived impact on the teachers’ performance, the theory of classroom observation naturally fits this study. According to de Abreu and Interpeler (2015), classroom behavior acts as a checkpoint for the learning process because it serves as an indicator of the learning extent. Therefore, it creates the need or progression. Hence, behavior becomes a pointer of the success achieved in the learning process and therefore outlines the remaining outset in the attainment of original objectives. By using classroom observation tool teachers’ behavior is cumulatively enriched. As a result, information during the school administrators/principals’ observation will be used to identify the strengths and components that needs to be improved in terms of the learning environment, student engagement, instructional quality, and curriculum implementation. Thus, will help teacher to address their needs in the teaching and learning process that can be used to promote quality education.

Consequently, another theory that support this study is the constructivism learning theory. Based on constructivist theories of learning, learners built their understanding as they construct their meanings for the knowledge they acquired. It must be noted that understanding is closely linked to learning, that is learning must consider the nature of knowledge to be taught. Therefore, teachers should involve students in the construction of knowledge and the creation of new ideas from what they already know. Hence, constructivism is a major

learning theory which is particularly applicable to the teaching and learning process.

Given this study’s focus on the tasks of the teachers and of the administrators, the theory of Bio-ecological systems of Urie Bronfenbrenner naturally fits this study. According to Bronfenbrenner (1986) as cited by Guy-Evans (2020), children develop within the complex systems of their changing environments. He considers interactions that occur at the five levels of the bio-ecological system. These interactions occur at the micro-, meso-, exo-, macro-, and chronosystem levels, which includes the family, community, school, friends, organizations, government, culture, and time. As the standardized classroom observation tool indicator number four emphasizes the creation of safe and secure learning environments so that learning can be enhanced in consonance with the implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedures, thus this theory deals how the surrounding environment of the child affects learning. Bronfenbrenner theory further emphasizes that children learn through interactions with their physical and social environment. Accordingly, the more opportunities learners engage with their parents the learning process, the more they likely to succeed. Hence, teachers’ interactions with the children, the activities they engage in together, as well as the social and physical environment are considered in understanding and learning the ecology of children’s worlds.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig 1: Framework of the Study.

The conceptual framework above shows the variables of the research on the teachers and school administrators’ perception on the use of standardized classroom evaluation tool. The conceptual framework of this study presents the teachers’ and school administrators perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in the teaching and learning process. Moreover, significant relationship between them was also tested by the researcher. Furthermore, challenges and the strategies used by the teachers and school administrators to cope with the challenges the encountered in using the standardized Classroom Observation Tool were also included

in the study. Based on the findings of the study, proposed action plan was made.

➤ *Research Questions*

This study examined the perceived impact of the Standardized Classroom Observation Tool among the school head/principals of Sultan Naga Dimaporo, Lanao del Norte.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the teachers in the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of:
 - 1.1 clarity of purpose; and
 - 1.2 usefulness in teaching and learning process?
2. What is the perception of the teachers in the use of standardized classroom?

➤ *Observation tool in terms of:*

- 2.1 clarity of purpose; and
- 2.2 usefulness in teaching and learning process?
3. Is there a significant difference between the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in teaching and learning process?
4. Based on the results of the study, what action plan can be proposed?

➤ *Research Hypothesis*

The researcher put forward that there is a significant difference between the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in teaching and learning process.

➤ *Definition of Terms*

To make this study more understandable to those might come across to it, the researcher included the definition of terms which enable them to have a clearer understanding of the queries they seek to answer. Thus, the following terms will be defined operationally and/or conceptually:

Action Plan. It is a detailed plan with specified actions that are needed to achieve a goal. It can also consist of a series of steps that must be taken to successfully complete a certain strategy (Toolshero.com, 2013). In this study, it refers to the plan to be proposed after the result of the study found.

Classroom Observation Tool (COT). It refers to a subset of the classroom evaluation used for the teachers. In this study, it refers to the instruments used by the school head/principal to rate the teachers during the mandatory classroom observation which will be done four times in a year.

Perception. From the Latin perception, meaning gathering or receiving) is the organization, identification, and interpretation of sensory information in order to represent and

understand the presented information or environment (Schacter, 2011). In his study, it refers to the teachers' and school administrators' insights on the use of standardized classroom observation tool.

Teacher. In this study, it refers a licensed professional individual engages in academic endeavor related to education.

School Administrators. In this study, it refers to the school principals and/or school heads who are considered as the raters during classroom observation tool.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the steps undertaken during the development, validation, and implementation of the questionnaire's perception of the teachers and school administrators on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. It is structured according to the following sections: research participants, research sampling, research design, research instruments, data gathering procedure, data analysis, triangulation, ethical considerations, and coding of data.

➤ *Participants*

The respondents of the study were the school administrators and teachers in Lanao del Norte. Purposive sampling technique was utilized to gather responses from the respondent's socio-demographic profile, perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Complete enumeration in choosing the teachers and school administrators, however only thirty had responded for the school administrators and eighty-nine for the teachers. different public schools in Sultan Naga Dimaporo, Lanao del Norte (Table 1). Furthermore, as shown in Table 2, the age of respondents was varied, hence, most of the teachers belongs to 28-33 years old while for the school administrators is seen to be varied ranging from 26 years old as the youngest while 62 years old as the oldest. This only means that an older or younger school administrators and teachers does not make any difference in their perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. In terms of the sex of the respondents, majority of the teachers and school administrators are females, hence, more responses were expected from female-teacher respondents than male-teacher respondents because, according to Esplada (2010) as cited by Alea, et. al. (2020) that DepEd records showed that 86 percent of the total population of teachers in Philippines are female. In terms of educational attainment majority of the teachers are with master's units while for school administrators most of them are master's degree holder. Moreover, majority of the teachers teaches for 1-5 years while most of the school administrators lead for 1-5 years. Consequently, most of the teachers belongs to large-sized school (26-100 number of teachers) while for the school administrators belongs to medium-sized schools (10-25 number of teachers).

Table 1: Number of Samples

	Population (N)	Samples (n)
Teachers	538	89
School Administrators	33	30
TOTAL	571	119

Table 2: Socio-demographic profile of the respondents.

Variable	Teachers		School Administrators		
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
Age	22-27	24	26.97	2	6.67
	28-33	37	41.57	7	18.82
	34-39	13	14.61	5	16.67
	40-45	9	10.11	5	16.67
	46-51	4	4.49	2	6.67
	52-57	2	2.25	8	26.67
Sex	58-63	0	0.00	1	3.33
	Male	16	17.98	11	36.67
Educational Status	Female	73	82.02	19	63.33
	Bachelor's Degree	12	13.48	0	0.00
	With Master's Unit	48	53.93	11	36.67
	Master's Degree Holder	28	31.46	12	40.00
	With Doctoral Unit	0	0.00	3	10.00
Number of Years in teaching	Doctoral Degree	1	1.12	4	13.33
	1-5 years	46	51.69		
	6-10 years	26	29.21		
	11-15 years	10	11.24		
	16-20 years	3	3.37		
	21-25 years	1	1.12		
Number of Years as School Head	26-30 years	3	3.37		
	1-5 years			13	43.33
	6-10 years			8	26.67
	11-15 years			3	10.00
	16-20 years			4	13.33
	21-25 years			1	3.33
School size	26-30 years			1	3.33
	Large School	33	37.08	9	30.00
	Medium School	32	35.96	14	46.67
	Small School	24	26.97	7	23.33

➤ Sampling

This study made use of the school administrators and teachers in Lanao del Norte as the respondents of the study. Teachers were chosen purposively since the ratees which has directly experience the implementation of the standardized classroom observation tool. Likewise, school administrators were also purposively chosen since they are the raters and they directly had the observations towards the teachers. Complete enumeration was done, wherein all teachers and school administrators in SND were given the questionnaire and was expected to respond the questionnaire given to them. However, only 30 among the 33 school administrators and 89 among the 538 teachers responded the questionnaire.

➤ Procedure

Data gathering procedure, started with the approval of the research topic by the research professor. After that, questionnaires were prepared. To determine the reliability of the questionnaire, pilot testing was done before hand. A total

of 30 teachers and school administrators who were not part of the study were asked to answer the survey questionnaire through Google forms which was sent via messenger application. Pilot testing was done to determine the preciseness of the instrument in measuring the variables related to this research. Before floating the instrument, this was first subjected to construct and content validity. Three validators were chosen to check validity of the items in each variable. They were identified as content experts, language experts and pedagogy experts. Factor analysis was also done to determine the items classification based on the preceding factors.

Moreover, the approved research questionnaire was then conducted. This was done through Google forms, which were sent to the respective DepEd school principals and teachers in Sultan Naga Dimaporo, Lanao del Norte via email and messenger application. To gain respondents approval in answering the survey questionnaire, informed consent was

also included in the questionnaire. Informed consent is one of the founding principles of research ethics. This was intended to determine if the respondents of the study took part on the research freely and voluntarily. Then, the respondents who voluntarily took part of the study, responded the questionnaire. After that, data gathered were tallied using MS 365 and was analyzed using SPSS software. Then, the results were evaluated and interpreted.

The figure below shows the flowchart of the data gathering procedure.

Fig 1: Flowchart of the data gathering procedure

➤ Design

This study used descriptive -survey design with qualitative support in gathering the data. Survey questionnaire was the main instrument of the study which was done on Google forms and was sent to the respective school administrators in Sultan Naga Dimaporo, Lanao del Norte. The present study surveyed the perceived impact of the school administrator on the standardized classroom observation tool. Descriptive design is quantitative research that tends to describe or interpret phenomenon, settings, or subjects as it exists naturally that attempts to gather quantifiable data for statistical analysis of the population sample. This was used in determining the respondent's socio demographic profile, school size, number of teachers, and the perception of the teachers and school administrators on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Moreover, challenges, and their coping strategies were also identified through an open-ended questionnaire.

➤ Ethical Consideration

During the conduct of the study, an informed consent will be sent to the respondents of the study. The process of obtaining consent consists of the following: consent should be given freely (voluntary) to the respondents. Furthermore, respondents should understand what is being asked of them, and involved persons must be competent to consent. This means, to participate in a research study, respondents itself need to be adequately informed about the research, comprehend the information, and have a power of freedom of choice to allow them to decide whether to participate or decline. Respondents' agreement to participation in this study will be obtained only after a thorough explanation of the research process. They will be required to sign the written informed consent. The potential respondents will be approached individually and will be explained on the purpose of the study and data collection process. They will be given an appropriate time to ask questions and address any concerns. It will be explained that as their participation is voluntary, refusing to participate or withdraw from the study while it is in progress would not affect their status as a person. An information sheet will be provided to further explain the study. The respondents will be given appropriate time (in this case: 24 hours up to one week) to read the information sheet and to decide whether they wanted to be involved in this study. They will be required to sign the informed consent form before the interview to indicate their permission to be part of the study and this signature will be confirmed prior to the conduct of the study. An explanation will be clearly given to the parents and respondents that they had a right to withdraw from the study at any time even after the informed consent will be signed. Consent to record the interview will also be asked from them. The respondents will be given an information sheet and informed consent will be available into English.

➤ Instruments

The questionnaire used was adopted and modified from the research of Wairimu (2016) (Appendix A) that studied the teachers' perception of classroom observation and checking of pupil's exercise books in Kenya. The survey questionnaire consisted of 25 items to know teachers and

school administrators perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool as well as its process. Each of the item by choosing an answer on the desired column based on the Likert Scale (4-Strongly Agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree, 1-Strongly Disagree). The questionnaire was divided into four parts. The first part dealt with socio-demographic profile of the respondents such as: age, sex, educational status, number of years in teaching (for teachers) and number of years as school administrator (for school administrators), school size. This part helped the researcher secure the respondents background information. The second part dealt with the perception of the teachers and school administrators on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Furthermore, the perception of teachers and school administrators. In constructing the indicators to determine the perceptions of the teachers and school administrators, parallelism technique was used. Parallelism uses similar words, phrases, or clauses to show that ideas have the same level of importance. Thus, each of the indicators believed to have an equal importance to both teachers and school administrators. Furthermore, this was used to identify the differences in the perception of the teachers and school administrators on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Third part dealt with the evaluation on the challenges encountered by the respondents and the coping strategies they used in handling the difficulties they encountered while using the standardized classroom observation tool. Before floating the instrument, this was first subjected to construct and content validity. Three validators were chosen to check validity of the items in each variable. They were identified as content experts, language experts and pedagogy experts. Factor analysis was also done to determine the items classification based on the preceding factors. In validating the questionnaire, the validators use the instrument of Pineda (2014), on his study on “Employee retention practices of multinational companies”. Based on the factor analysis, items on the perception of the teachers and school administrators on the standardized classroom observation tool were classified into clarity of purpose and usefulness in teaching and learning process. To determine the reliability of the questionnaire, pilot testing was done before hand. A total of 30 teachers and school administrators who were not part of the study were asked to answer the survey questionnaire through Google forms which was sent via messenger

application. Pilot testing was done to determine the preciseness of the instrument in measuring the variables related to this research. The computation of the reliability test using Cronbach Alpha was made through PSPP. It was found out that the instrument has an acceptable internal consistency having obtained a Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of 0.76. Rondaris, Ibañez and Varela (2014) contend that an instrument’s score is only interpretable when it possesses a substantial internal consistency and when each item in the instrument measures the same construct as the rest of the items. Thus, determining the internal consistency correlations are essentially measuring of homogeneity, using Cronbach’s Alpha, since this is widely use in measuring items internal consistency. After the face validation and the reliability test, identified strengths of the questionnaire were reinforced while its weaknesses were modified. Comments were considered and suggestions were accommodated during the revision of the survey questionnaire. As a result, final survey questionnaire was generated preceding its implementation.

➤ *Data Analysis and Statistical Tools*

The survey questionnaire consisted of 10 items to know their perceived impact of standardized classroom observation tool as well as its process. Each of the item by choosing an answer on the desired column based on the Likert Scale (4-Strongly Agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree, 1-Strongly Disagree). For the data analysis, the computer software PSPP and MS Excel 365 were used to process data. The statistical tools which were used in the analysis and interpretation of data and hypotheses testing include descriptive and inferential statistics, specifically weighted mean and t-test for unpaired data. Thematic analysis was used to the responses of the respondents in the open-ended question on the coping strategies they used in handling the challenges they encountered in using the standardized classroom observation tool

In interpreting the answer, the researcher used Likert Scale (1988) as used by Wairimu (2016) weighted mode of that studies the teacher’s perception of classroom evaluation and checking of pupil’s exercise books in Kenya. The summated rating scale with its point score range intervals and verbal equivalent are as follows:

Response Options	Range Intervals	Positive Item Weighted Scale	Verbal equivalent Scale	Negative Item Weighted Scale	Verbal Equivalent Scale
Strongly Agree	3.26-4.00	4	Highly Positive	1	Highly Positive
Agree	2.51-3.25	3	Positive	2	Positive
Disagree	1.76-2.50	2	Negative	3	Negative
Strongly Disagree	1.00-1.75	1	Highly Negative	4	Highly Negative

Table :- Data analysis and statistical tools

➤ *Coding of Respondents*

In presenting the responses of the school head/principal in the interview, codes were used. Teachers were coded as TR1, TR2, TR3, TR4 and so forth while school administrators were coded as SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4 and so forth.

VII. RESULTS, DISCUSSIONS

➤ *Teachers Perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of Clarity of Purpose*

Table 2 presents the perception of the teachers on the standardized classroom observation tool as to clarity of purpose. Generally, teachers have positive perceptions on the use of standardized classroom evaluation tool when it comes

to the clarity of each purpose, as reflected on the grand weighted mean of 3.28 with the standard deviation of 0.38. Teachers see that the tool positively made by the professionals for the purpose of helping teachers to be effective in their chosen field. Moreover, T22, appreciated the flexibility of the standardized classroom observation tool for it positively serve its purpose good enough for the success of teaching and learning (T25).

As can be gleaned in the table, in item, teachers are highly positive on the statement that; The standardized classroom observation tool guides us in assessing our own teaching performance As opined by TR29 that the tool is part of the teacher's professional growth, thus through this tool they may be able to evaluate the effectivity and efficiency of their teaching techniques and strategies to meet the desired learning outcomes. Consequently, TR13 said that the standardized classroom observation tool really helps the teachers in improving their ways of teaching the learners. Concerning this, Suparto (2020), quality of teaching and learning can be improved if there is academic supervision with classroom observation techniques.

In item 2, respondents positively agreed that the mode of verification in the traditional tool were emphasized compared to the new observation tool. This is supported with the statement of TR10 mentioning that if one cannot understand the mode of verifications in the tool, then it is very hard to get a grade of 7 (highest grade).

In the next item, item 3, respondents rated highly positive on the statement: *The mode of verification in the tool accurately describes teacher's expected performance. This clearly shown that teachers believe that the mode of verification in tools defines what is expected to them during observation.* This is contrast with the statement of TR15, who said that being not aware in the mode of verifications in the tool is a problem that is encountered in using the tool.

In item 4, respondents highly positive agreed that the classroom observation tool gives them a good understanding of my own classroom culture. This is in contrast with the statement of TR14, revealing that the classroom observation tool takes a lot of time to see to it if the mode of verification covers what is found in the classroom, thus, there is a need to reassess the tool.

Likewise, in the 5th item, respondents rated highly positive on the statements that; *The classroom observation tool helped us to be more knowledgeable in the use of ICT.* This clearly shows that the tool helps them to improve their knowledge on the use of ICT. As supported by TR15, saying that apart from the stress brought by the tool during observation it still has it benefits since it helps them to improve their skills in ICT.

Consequently, in 6th statement, respondents rated highly positive on the indicator that; *The classroom observation tool is enough to determine the success of the teaching and learning process.* Thus, they believed that the tool helps them to determine their success in the teaching and learning

process. However, this negates with the statement of TR80, that success in the teaching and learning process can be determine even without the use of the tool.

Moreover, in the item 7, it is clearly reflected that respondents clearly understands the purpose of using the standardized classroom observation tool which is use evaluate their teaching performance. Similarly, this negates the statement of T80, that success in the teaching and learning process can be determine even without the use of the tool.

In the next item, in item 8, respondents negatively believe that the tool burden teachers who are not knowledgeable in the use of ICT. This agrees with what TR40 mentioned that the integrating ICT in the teaching-learning process is a burden to them since, their school do not have complete equipment in support with the use of ICT. Moreover, TR26, also mentioned that she had a problem on integrating ICT since she is not well-equipped with the use of technology. However, TR15, believed that integrating ICT in the lesson, helps them to be more knowledgeable in the use of technology.

In item 9, respondents rated highly positive on the statement that, the mode of verification in the standardized classroom observation tool has help them to be reflective on our teaching practice. This is in relation to the pre-conference and post-conference done during before and after the observation. In the study of Barrogo (2020), feedback received by teachers during post conference were enough for them to reflect their classroom teaching techniques and strategies.

In the next item, item 10, respondents have a highly positive belief that the tool allows the school administrators to spend adequate time observing us to have basis in assessing our performance. Thus, this can be inferred that the standardized classroom observation tool significantly helps the school administrators to assess the performances of their teachers. However, TR19, school administrators as observers have their own preferences on that good teaching looks like; thus, some of them makes judgements based on emotional responses (TR16).

Similarly, in item 11, respondents have highly positive belief that: *The standardized classroom observation tool is consistent what constitutes effective teaching.* However, this negates the statement of T24, that success in the teaching and learning process can be determine even without the use of the tool.

However, in item 12, teachers found it negative on the indicator that the classroom observation tool is enough to determine the success of the teaching and learning process. The results, contradicted on the findings of Barrogo (2020), which noted that majority (86%) of the respondents believed that the standardized classroom observation tool was enough to determine the success of the teaching and learning. As mentioned by TR19, that using the standardized classroom observation tool is not adequate for a full assessment, thus there is a need for supplementary assessments. Furthermore,

TR11 noted that the tool does not provide clear, detailed, and accurate support to teachers' performance, hence TR24 reflected that some of the MOV's are difficult to achieve in certain learning competencies. This was further verified by TR80 when she specifies that the tool needs only to be followed as it is required in the RPMS, thus an effective and efficient teacher is always evident even without the tool.

In the next item, item 13, found it to be highly positive on the statement that *the standardized classroom observation tool gives us knowledge on what to expect during the observation process*. This is in line, with the pre-conference done beforehand before the observation process. Through this, teachers may realize that needs to be improved during the observation process.

Furthermore, in item 14, respondents agreed to have a highly positive rate on the statements that; *The mode of verifications (MOV's) in the tool accurately describes our teaching performance*. Similarly, this is contrast with the statement of TR15, who said that being not aware in the mode

of verifications in the tool is a problem that is encountered in using the tool.

The last item, in item 15, results revealed that respondents are highly positive in terms of the satisfaction on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. This corroborates with concept of Jimenez (2020), when he mentioned that if the attitude of teachers towards their work is high, satisfaction level will also be positively high.

Consequently, teachers rated highly positive on the first indicator; The standardized classroom observation tool guides us in assessing our own teaching performance while 12th indicator (The standardized classroom observation tool is accurate to get enough annotation of our performance) was rated negative among the teachers. Therefore, it is evident to say that teachers believe that the standardized classroom observation tool had guide them in the assessment of their own performance however, they found that the mode of verifications must accurately identify the performance that needs to be observed.

Table 2: Teachers' perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool (n=30).

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal interpretation
1.The standardized classroom observation tool guides us in assessing our own teaching performance.	3.64	0.51	Highly Positive
2. The mode of verifications in the traditional tool were emphasized compared to the new observation tool.	3.16	0.69	Positive
3. The mode of verification in the tool accurately describes our expected performance.	3.42	0.58	Highly Positive
4. The classroom observation tool gives me a good understanding of my own classroom culture.	3.51	0.52	Highly Positive
5. The classroom observation tool helped us to be more knowledgeable in the use of ICT.	3.52	0.61	Highly Positive
6. The classroom observation tool is enough to determine the success of the teaching and learning process.	3.29	0.69	Highly Positive
7. I clearly understand the purpose of using the standardized classroom observation tool to evaluate my own teaching performance.	3.56	0.52	Highly Positive
8. The classroom observation tool burden us teachers who are not knowledgeable in the use of ICT.	2.63	0.91	Negative
9. The mode of verification in the standardized classroom observation tool has help us to be reflective on our teaching practice.	3.51	0.57	Highly Positive
10. The tool allows the school administrators to spend adequate time observing us to have basis in assessing our performance.	3.46	0.58	Highly Positive
11. The standardized classroom observation tool is consistent what constitutes effective teaching.	3.37	0.55	Highly Positive
12. The standardized classroom observation tool is accurate to get enough annotation of our performance.	2.15	0.92	Negative
13. The standardized classroom observation tool gives us knowledge on what to expect during the observation process.	3.49	0.50	Highly Positive
14. The mode of verifications (MOV's) in the tool accurately describes our teaching performance.	3.36	0.63	Highly Positive
15. I am satisfied with the standardized classroom observation tool.	3.39	0.56	Highly Positive
Grand Weighted Mean	3.30	0.38	Highly Positive

➤ *Teachers Perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of Usefulness in the teaching and learning process*

Table 3 discloses the teachers' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of the usefulness in the teaching and learning process.

Generally, the result shows that the standardized classroom observation tool positive useful in the teaching and learning process. The results below are parallel to the statement of T22, saying that "I appreciate how flexible the standardized classroom observation is. It changes as the needs of the society change. And as it evolves, I just hope that it considers the situation of the teachers and learners in underdeveloped areas".

As reflected in the table, in item 1, respondents positively believed that the classroom observation tool helped enhance the relationship between the teachers and the administrators. During the post conferences, teachers freely express their opinions and can clarify what could have been unclear on the side of the school heads during class observations. Through this, school heads can understand the teachers experience in the real classroom scenario.

Furthermore, in item number 2, teachers still positively believed that standardized classroom evaluation tool guides us and on our teaching profession (WM=2.53; SD=1.05). This is a clear evident that the tool guided the teachers and their profession as well. As supported by the statement of TR12 mentioning the advantage for having the tool in the teaching process.

Similarly, in item 3 revealed the results that the teachers positively preferred the traditional observation tool compared to the revised classroom observation tool. An open-ended question was given by the teachers on the challenge they encountered in the use of the standardized classroom observation tool. Results shown that the nature of the tool was a problem to the teachers. As for T17, the mode of verifications on the tool is hard to understand. T14, verified that the new classroom observation tool has a higher standard than the old one and that makes it more challenging. Additionally, T24 mentioned that:

This classroom observation tool somehow gives me stress because this requires additional evidence or MOVs. Making the lesson plan and instructional materials takes a lot of time since you must see to it that all the indicators were covered but on the other side, it helps us improve our skills in ICT, classroom management and our teaching styles and strategies for a more manageable and meaningful teaching and learning process.

Item 4 stated that teachers positively agreed that the classroom observation tool leads to the improvement of the teaching and learning process. As supported by Barrogo (2020), through classroom observation, teacher's performance can be improved through different parameters is vital in achieving quality education.

Item 5 positively revealed that the standardized classroom observation tool has encouraged the school administrators to effectively discuss teachers teaching practices in the classroom. The constructive criticisms of the school heads help the teachers to be more confident in their teachings and to improve themselves.

In the next item, item 6, teachers responded positively wherein they believed that the classroom observation tool helped us to grow professionally. This is a clear evident that the tool guided the teachers and their profession as well. As supported by the statement of TR52 mentioning the advantage for having the tool in the teaching process.

In item 7, teachers responded negatively on the indicator that the classroom observation tool help teachers to grow and improve learners' learning. According to TR16, one of the difficulties in using the standardized classroom observation tool, is when you have large number of pupils in frustration level, thus it is hard for them to determine if there is an improve in learning. Moreover, TR66 reinforced that the mode of verification in the COT, does not clearly identify what to expect from the learners since learners think differently. TR17 added that there are indicators which is not applicable to their learners.

In item 8, respondents positively agreed that the standardized classroom observation tool is significant to them and to their profession. As mentioned by TR29, that the "standardized classroom observation tool is a part of our professional growth wherein we are able to evaluate how effective our techniques and strategies in teaching our learners".

In the 9th item, respondents rated highly positive on the statement that the standardized classroom observation tool clearly describes the performance of the teachers to be observed. This in contrast with the statement of TR03, saying that complying the indicators stated in the tool is a challenge to them. As mentioned by TR19, "the indicators on the classroom observation tool should be detailed, specific, and measurable for the specific context, grade, and type of lesson (for example, a grade 1 reading lesson).

The last item, item 10, rated positive by the respondents. Thus, this can be inferred that respondent positively perceived the standardized classroom observation tool. This is notable as mentioned by TR05, that the classroom observation tool can assess teachers' performance and can used to plan for improvement, however it can create stress and test the confidence of the teacher being observed.

Specifically, the teachers rated highly positive on the indicator: *The standardized classroom observation tool clearly describes the performance of the teachers to be observed*. While negative on the indicator: *The classroom observation tool help teachers to grow and improve learners' learning*.

Table 3: Teachers Perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of Usefulness in the teaching and learning process(n=30).

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal interpretation
1. The classroom observation tool helped to enhance the relationship between the teachers and the administrators	2.56	1.02	Positive
2. The standardized classroom observation tool guides us and on our teaching profession	2.51	1.07	Positive
3. I prefer the traditional evaluation tool compared to the revised classroom observation tool.	2.53	0.80	Positive
4. The classroom observation tool leads to improvement of the teaching and learning.	2.82	1.08	Positive
5. The standardized classroom observation tool has encouraged the school administrators to effectively discuss my own teaching practices in the classroom	2.66	0.95	Positive
6. The classroom observation tool helped us to grow professionally.	2.80	1.07	Positive
7. The classroom observation tool help teachers to grow and improve learners' learning.	1.93	0.96	Negative
8. The standardized classroom observation tool is significant to teachers and their teaching profession.	2.84	1.00	Positive
9. The standardized classroom observation tool clearly describes the performance of the teachers to be observed.	3.33	0.65	Highly Positive
10. The standardized classroom observation tool is significant to the teachers in teaching-learning process.	2.88	1.06	Positive
Grand Weighted Mean	2.69	0.59	Positive

➤ *School Administrators Perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of Clarity of Purpose*

Table 4 reveals the school administrators' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation in terms of clarity of purpose.

Generally, school administrators have a high positive belief that the standardized classroom evaluation tool have a clear purpose in the teaching and learning process. However, SA04 suggested that an intensified training and workshop must be done so that indicators must be clearly understood by the teachers, since they have different understanding on the indicators (SA07).

As reflected on the table, in item 1, school administrators have a highly positive perception that the standardized classroom observation tool guides them in assessing the performance of the teachers. Thus, they believed that the tool is an important avenue to assess the performance of the teachers.

In item 2, school administrators, positively believe that the mode of verification in traditional tool was emphasized compared to the new observation. Thus, it makes sense that mode of verifications in the traditional tool clearly describes are more emphasized. This in contrast with the statement of SA25, stating that the indicator in the new tool is realistic.

The next item, item 3, school administrators rated highly positive on the statement that; *The mode of verification in the tool accurately describes the expected teachers' performance.* This is in line with the statement of SA04, stating that, "indicators in the tool were not stated

specifically, thus it makes us hard to give an appropriate expectation on the teacher's performance.

Moreover, in item 4, similarly, school administrators have a highly positive belief that the tool gives them a good understanding on their teacher's classroom culture. Through this, school administrators may be able to understand the nature of the teaching and learning process.

Consequently, in item 5, school administrators, have a high positive belief that the classroom observation tool had helps their teachers to be more knowledgeable with the use of ICT. This is in contrast with the statement of SA15, stating that "in using the standardized classroom observation tools are the teacher's readiness in the use of ICT, particularly retireable teachers who are not computer literate".

In item 6, school administrators are still highly positive on the statement that the tool is enough to determine the success of the teaching and learning process. However, SA04, stated that, "indicators in the tool were not stated specifically, thus it makes us hard to give an appropriate expectation on the teacher's performance".

In the next item, which is item 7, it is clearly reflected that school administrators are highly positive understanding on the purpose of using the standardized classroom observation tool to evaluate the teachers' teaching performance of teachers. However, SA06, mentioned that there are teachers who cannot meet their expectations during the classroom observation". Thus, it is clear to say that there is a problem on determining the teacher's teaching performance through only the use of the tool. This is further

supported by TR23 when she specifies that an effective and efficient teacher is always evident even without the tool.

As for the 8th item, school administrators negatively agreed on the statement that: *The classroom observation tool burden teachers who are not knowledgeable with the use of ICT.* This agrees with the results in item 5, when school administrators have a highly positive rate on the statement that the tool had helped teachers to become more knowledgeable in integrating ICT in teaching-learning process.

Additionally, in item 9, school administrators, highly positive in their perception that the tool helps the teachers' to be more reflective on their performance when the tool was used. This is in relation to the pre-conference and post-conference done during before and after the observation. In the study of Barrogo (2020), feedback received by teachers during post conference were enough for them to reflect their classroom teaching techniques and strategies.

Furthermore, in item 10, on the statement that; *the tool allows them (school administrators) to spend adequate time observing teachers to form basis to assess their performance,* school administrators rated highly positive. This is contrast with what SA12 stated, "I believed that teacher's performance cannot be measured by simply being observed quarterly". This has something to do with the authenticity of the teachers' performance with or without school administrators doing the classroom observation.

In the next, item 11, school administrators have a similar belief which is highly positive on the statement, that: *The standardized classroom observation tool is consistent what constitutes effective teaching.* However, going back to the statement of SA12 stating that teacher's performance cannot be measured by simply being observed quarterly. Thus, it can be said that effective teaching does not only happen during

observation, but this must also be an attitude that every teacher must possess.

In the 12th statement, the school administrators negatively perceived that the standardized classroom observation tool is accurate to get enough annotation of the teachers' performance. This has something to do with how observers rated their teachers during observation. As mentioned by both teachers and school administrators, sometimes emotions can be included during the observations which make judgements bias.

In the next item, in item 13, the school administrators rated highly positive on the statement that; *The standardized classroom observation tool gives the teacher knowledge on what to expect to them during the observation process.* However, SA25, said that indicators in the tool are not all realistic, hence, some indicators were not stated specifically.

In item 14, school administrators have a high positive belief that the mode of verifications (MOV's) in the tool accurately describes the teachers' performance. This is in contrast with the statement of SA19, that there are a lot of things that needs to be remembered, developed, and enhanced, to making it more realistic.

In the last item, school administrators have a high positive satisfaction on the use of standardized classroom observation tool. However, school administrators reflected that there are problems they encountered with how the standardized classroom observation tool is use.

It is clearly observed that both teachers and school administrators, has a highly positive belief that, *The standardized classroom observation tool guides us in assessing teachers' performance.* Similarly, they both are both negative on the statement that, *The standardized classroom observation tool is accurate to get enough annotation of the teachers' performance.*

Table 4: School Administrators perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of clarity of purpose (n=30).

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal interpretation
1. The standardized classroom observation tool guides us in assessing teachers' performance.	3.67	0.48	Highly Positive
2. The mode of verifications in the traditional tool were emphasized compared to the new observation tool.	2.77	0.82	Positive
3. The mode of verification in the tool accurately describes the expected teachers' performance.	3.43	0.50	Highly Positive
4. The classroom observation tool gives me a good understanding on my teacher's classroom's culture.	3.47	0.51	Highly Positive
5. The classroom observation tool helped teachers to be more knowledgeable with the use of ICT.	3.43	0.57	Highly Positive
6. The classroom observation tool is enough to determine the success of the teaching and learning process.	3.37	0.61	Highly Positive
7. I clearly understand the purpose of using the standardized classroom observation tool to evaluate the teachers' teaching performance of teachers	3.57	0.50	Highly Positive
8. The classroom observation tool burden teachers who are not knowledgeable with the use of ICT.	2.70	0.75	Negative

9. The mode of verification in the standardized classroom observation tool has help teachers to be reflective in their practice.	3.57	0.50	Highly Positive
10. The tool allows us to spend adequate time observing teachers to form basis to assess their performance	3.50	0.51	Highly Positive
11. The standardized classroom observation tool is consistent what constitutes effective teaching.	3.30	0.47	Highly Positive
12. The standardized classroom observation tool is accurate to get enough annotation of the teachers' performance.	2.03	0.96	Negative
13. The standardized classroom observation tool gives the teacher knowledge on what to expect to them during the observation process.	3.60	0.50	Highly Positive
14. The mode of verifications (MOV's) in the tool accurately describes the teachers' performance.	3.43	0.50	Highly Positive
15. I am satisfied with the standardized classroom observation tool.	3.37	0.56	Highly Positive
Grand Weighted Mean	3.28	0.32	Highly Positive

➤ *School Administrators Perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of Usefulness in the teaching and learning process*

Table 5 discloses the school administrators' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of the usefulness in the teaching and learning process. As shown in the table, in item 1, school administrators have a negative belief that the classroom observation tool helped enhanced the relation between the teachers and the school administrators. This has something with to do with what SA13 said, that "teachers disagree the grades they received during classroom observation, hence this cause conflict between the teachers and the school administrators. However, teachers agreed that using this tool they can freely express their opinions and can clarify what could have been unclear on the side of the school heads during class observations. Through this, school heads can understand the teachers experience in the real classroom scenario.

In item 2, school administrators negatively responded on the statement that: *The standardized classroom observation tool guides the teachers and their teaching profession.* For SA06, there are teachers who cannot meet what is expected to them during observation, that is this disable the tool to guide their profession. Likewise, SA5, said that "there are teachers who do not treat the tool seriously and not reflective on their performance.

Similarly, in item 3, respondents are negative on the statement that they prefer traditional evaluation tool compared to the revised classroom observation tool. As SA04, indicators (mode of verification) in the tool are not stated specifically and needs to be realistic. However, this is in contrast with the teacher's perception that they positively preferred the traditional tool than the new tool.

In the 4th item, school administrators positively agreed that the tool had helped teachers improve their teaching and learning process. However, SA05 mentioned that ample time must be given for the orientation in the use of the tool, so that teachers will be given a chance to improve their performance from the first observation up to the 4th observation, hence this is done quarterly.

In item 5, school administrators are negative on the statement that the tool has encouraged them to effectively discuss teacher's teaching practices in the classroom. Hence, this is in consonance with what SA13 mentioned, when she said that, "there are teachers who disagreed with the grades they received during classroom observation." This is further supported with SA02 revelations that conflict arose when teachers have their own interpretation on the indicators in the tool. This clearly shows that discussing to the teachers their performance is sometimes a problem.

In the 6th item, school administrators positively perceived that the tool had helped teachers to grow professionally. According to SA20, if teachers applied all the suggestions and comments during the observation, teachers may be able to help themselves grow professional. As to SA07, teachers need to study, understand, and reflect the benefits of the standardized classroom observation tool.

Furthermore, in the 7th item, school administrators negatively perceived that the classroom observation tool fails to help teachers to grow and improve learners' learning. It implies that school administrators positively perceived that the tools help improve learners' learning engagement. However, it is contrast on what SA15 mentioned, that the tool should put more emphasis on the student's learning outcomes.

In the 8th item, school administrators positively believe that the standardized classroom observation tool is significant to teachers and their teaching profession. This is similar to the reflected response in item 6. Therefore, it can be inferred that school administrators understand the usefulness of the tool in the teaching profession.

Moreover, item 9 is the only item rated highly positive by the school administrators. Thus, the believed that the standardized classroom observation tool clearly describes the performance of the teachers to be observed. However, SA03, SA04, SA19 and SA25, said that the mode of verifications indicated in the tool is not realistic, specific and therefore needs to be enhanced and upgraded.

In the last item, school administrators positive perceived the significance of the standardized classroom observation tool to the teachers in teaching-learning process. However, to meet this, there is a need to have an in depth understanding to the mode of verification indication (SA07), that is technical assistance must be given to the teachers (SA02). As suggested by SA01, school administrators must be reoriented and crisscross observation must be employed, so that judgements must be based on the specified criteria and not on emotional state.

Additionally, the standardized classroom observation tool in terms of the usefulness in the teaching and learning

process as perceived by the school administrators is generally positive with a grand weighted mean 2.55. This means that school administrators believed that the tool had helped teachers in the teaching and learning process. However, suggestions were made, as to reorientation between teachers and school administrators on the understanding of the tool and enhancing the indicators making it more realistic and related to the real classroom teaching and learning scenario. Moreover, SA13, suggested that aside from the standardized classroom observation tool, additional tool must also be presented (checklists) during observation.

Table 5: School Administrators perception on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool in terms of usefulness in the teaching and learning process (n=30).

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal interpretation
1. The classroom observation tool helped to enhance the relationship between the teachers and the administrators	2.37	1.16	Negative
2. The standardized classroom observation tool guides the teachers and their teaching profession.	2.17	1.09	Negative
3. I prefer the traditional evaluation tool compared to the revised classroom observation tool.	2.50	0.90	Negative
4. The classroom observation tool leads to improvement of the teaching and learning.	2.57	1.14	Positive
5. The standardized classroom observation tool has encouraged me to effectively discuss teacher's teaching practices in the classroom	2.47	1.01	Negative
6. The classroom observation tool helped teachers to grow professionally.	2.63	1.10	Positive
7. The classroom observation tool fails to help teachers to grow and improve learners' learning.	2.03	0.93	Negative
8. The standardized classroom observation tool is significant to teachers and their teaching profession.	2.70	1.06	Positive
9. The standardized classroom observation tool clearly describes the performance of the teachers to be observed	3.47	0.57	Highly Positive
10. The standardized classroom observation tool is significant to the teachers in teaching-learning process.	2.57	1.14	Positive
Grand Weighted Mean	2.55	0.62	Positive

➤ *Difference between the perception of the teachers and school administrators on the use of the standardized classroom observation tool.*

A t-test for paired observation was done to find out whether the mean difference is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Table 6 illustrates the difference between teachers' and school administrations' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in the teaching and learning process.

As reflected on the table, the mean scores of the teachers' perception and school administrators on the clarity of purpose are 3.30 and 3.28, respectively, thus an increase of the mean score of 0.04. Moreover, an increase in the mean difference between the teachers and school administrators in terms of their perception in usefulness of the tool in the teaching and learning process, wherein a mean difference of 0.14 is observed.

Moreover, Table 6 further shows that the t-test value of 0.765 in the in the first pair (clarity of purpose) and 0.219 in the second pair (usefulness in the teaching and learning process), respectively, is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, it is enough to accept the hypothesis of no significant difference between the perception of the teachers and the school administrator on the use of standardized tool in terms of clarity of purpose and its usefulness in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, it matches the results in the weighted mean that both teachers and school administrators have a highly positive perception in terms of the tool's clarity of purpose and positive perception in terms of its usefulness in the teaching and learning process. Thus, teachers and school administrators have a similar perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool.

Table 6: Difference between teachers’ and school administrations’ perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in the teaching and learning process.

Perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool		Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference	T-test	Remarks
Clarity of Purpose	Teachers	3.30	0.38	0.04	0.282	Ho Accepted
	School Administrators	3.28	0.32			
Usefulness in the teaching and learning process	Teachers	2.69	0.56	0.14	1.083	Ho Accepted
	School Administrators	2.55	0.62			

Ho: There is no significant difference between the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in teaching and learning process.

➤ *Challenges encountered by teachers and school administrators on the use of the Standard Classroom Observation Tool*

To strengthen the results of the study and for the purpose of understanding the insights of the teachers and school administrators on the use of the standardized classroom observation tool, they are asked to identify the challenges they encountered in using the tool. The first identified challenge concerns with the **student’s ability to understand and engagement in learning**. TR4 and TR16 express that they had have trouble in to administer a class using the tool especially when many pupils are in frustration. Thus, T66 noted that since learners are thinking differently, therefore they process information in different manner, hence that is how teachers are being observed. SA15, added that there is a need to put more emphasis on the student’s learning engagement.

Teachers indicated that they find it difficult to achieve **objectives and positive learning outcomes**. As mentioned by TR6, “the challenging part in using the standardized classroom observation tool is when you need to carefully design the lesson to make it realistic”. Moreover, TR76 said that:

One of the challenges I encountered in using the standardized classroom observation tool is formulating the lesson plan with techniques and strategies that would meet the targets in the COT and at the same time making the learning objectives SMART— Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-bound without compromising the needs of my diverse learners.

Both teachers and school administrators that **lack of awareness on the indicators** is another challenge in using the standardized classroom observation tool. According to TR15, one of the challenges she encountered in using the tool is her lack of awareness in the indicators. TR9 added that, “the indicators are not specific in every part of the lesson”. Furthermore, TR17 and TR84, emphasizes that some of the indicators are not applicable to all learners, thus, they find difficulty in achieving the learning competency. TR21, noted that there are additional indicators in the tool which is hard to realize. Thus, it makes sense that teachers need to be familiar with the indicators in stipulated in the standardized classroom observation tool. For the school administrators, SA08, that

they have different understanding on the indicators stated, thus there is a need to have an in depth understanding to all of the indicators in the tool.

One of the indicators in the standardized classroom observation tool, is the integrating the lesson across curriculum teaching areas. However, this in turn one of the difficulties identified by the teachers in using the tool, as emphasized by, TR25, TR27, and TR28. Teachers and school administrators find it hard to integrate competencies within and across curriculum. **Insufficient instructional materials which include integrating the use of ICT in the lesson** is another difficulty identified by the teachers. In using standardized classroom observation tool, availability of learning materials and the availability of technology especially ICT is a common problem (TR18 and TR22). Furthermore, T40 stated that:

In the standardized classroom observation tool, we do have an ICT integration that is already belong in the indicator that a teacher will be evaluated during the observation. One of the challenges that I encountered was integrating ICT in the teaching - learning process it is because in our school we don't have a complete equipment that will be used during the classroom observation.

Moreover, SA12 said that, “the challenges encountered in using the standardized classroom evaluation observation tools are the teacher's readiness to use ICT, particularly those soon to retire teachers who are not computer literate” For that it is suggested that teachers must be provided with more ICT training (S15).

Another problem identified by the teachers and school administrators, is the **observer’s preference**. Teachers find inconsistency on how observers make judgements on their performance.

According to TR19, TR36 and TR60, classroom observers make judgements based on an emotional response, they have their own preferences on what good teaching looks like. Moreover, school administrators themselves found this a challenge. As mentioned by SA01, Instructional leader might have their own preferences on what good teaching looks like and can project that as they complete the observation instrument.

Preparation is the last challenge identified by the teachers in using the standardized classroom observation tool. TR58 said that:

The challenge I encountered in using the standardized classroom observation tool is during the preparation of the lesson wherein I need to look for activities that suits to needs of the learners and at the same time fits and hits the criterion of the classroom observation form use in our department that is sometimes difficult to achieve.

TR59 added:

There are varieties of challenges that a teacher might encounter during classroom observation, in my case, the most challenging part of the COT is the preparation stage, because there are indicators that are very hard to achieve specially during the pandemic. When the preparation is done then everything will smoothly follow as planned.

However, school administrators, confirmed itself that the **nature of the tool** is a problem itself. As mentioned by SA25, the tool use is not realistic at all, and indicators are not stated specifically (SA04). Moreover, SA08 opined that they have different understanding of the different indicators.

Teachers and School Administrators Coping Strategies

As teachers face different challenges in using the standardized classroom observation tool, they strive to overcome such challenges through different approaches. Teachers are still adaptable and open for possible changes, as TR69 said that being open minded and ready to accept any suggestions from others is a key to overcome challenges in using the standardized classroom observation tool.

Based on the responses of the respondents to the open-ended question given to them various strategies were given to cope with the challenges they encountered using the standardized classroom observation tool.

Time Management is an important aspect that a teacher and school administrators must possess to handle daily tasks easily. This can be done through making schedules on the different activities they are in to and balancing their tasks. If a teacher has that ability, they may be able to know what they need to prioritize. As stated by TR80, “time management is one of the effective ways to cope with the challenges along with proper planning”. SA16 said that instructional supervision matrix should be followed to avoid conflict of schedules. According to Sari and Nayir (2020), organizing classroom management can be used as a strategy to deal with the challenges encountered in education.

The standardized classroom observation tool serves as a guide for the teachers to assess their performance and plan for their improvement, thus, enhancement of **teachers’ preparation and competency**. Because of this, updating knowledge and skills and by being resourceful teachers may be able to cope with the challenges they encountered in using the tool. As for TR18, “be resourceful and be updated by searching more effective strategies”. Importance of being resourceful is emphasized by the following teachers:

As a teacher you should be resourceful in everything that are related to your work, to cope up with all the challenges that may encounter. The utilization of technology

and teaching tools, instructional materials are prepared ahead of time, and to provide varied instructional assessment to cater the learning ability of the learners as well as establish conducive classroom environment to learn—TR36—

As a teacher in the 21st century, we should be innovative in dealing with the teaching-learning processes. There are many ways that we can do for us to comply such indicator especially in the ICT integration. By that, being an innovative teacher, we can find other ways for us to cope such challenges that we will be encountering--TR41--

TR6, TR15, TR31 and TR38, opined that peer tutoring, technical assistance, and constant communication to more knowledgeable others are very important in to cope in any challenges relating to the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Sari and Nayir (2020) found out in their study that getting help from colleagues and constant communication using different communication tools are some of the ways teachers can handle challenges in using standardized classroom observation tool. Importance of constant of communication and seeking help to others was emphasized by TR54:

I always look for support from my school head and co-teachers. I would love to ask for their suggestions for the improvement of my lesson specially in the pre-conference. I also give enough time in making my lesson plan and instructional materials to avoid unnecessary things to happen. I also love to ask for feedback after the observation. This will help me know my weaknesses and strengths that I may improve for the next observation.

Likewise, school administrators said that giving more technical assistance is one way to cope with the challenges encountered in the use of standardized classroom observation tool. Both SA02, SA04 and SA06, said that giving technical assistance is one way to help teachers to perform their best during the observation process. This can be done by calling the attention of the teacher concern so that technical assistance can be easily given to them to improve their manner of handling the class (SA20).

Being prepared all the time is another way to cope with the challenges they encountered in using the tool. As mentioned by TR49, “ being prepared all the time and thinking that every day is an evaluation day is a way in dealing with those challenges”. Their preparedness had lessened their burdens and that it helped to overcome the challenges calmly and intelligently. They believe that being prepared helps them to be more confident that they can accomplished the indicators in the COT. Being prepared was articulated by the following teachers:

I cope with the challenges I encounter using the standardized classroom evaluation tool by making or preparing the lesson ahead and earlier from the scheduled day of observation, so I have ample time to check and make changes in the lesson and to align all the teaching and learning process in the criteria of the observation tool.—TR58—

Teacher should be well-prepared before the classroom observation to have a smooth delivery of topic and or discussion to the class. Before the classroom observation is observed, I find myself asking help from my colleagues specially to my seniors on how to achieve those indicators that are somehow difficult to achieved, I sometimes ask tips from my school head what to do to have a good rate during pre-conference, a meeting prior to classroom observation. — TR59—

The results of the study also showed that self-learning is another way to helped teachers overcome the challenges they encountered in using the standardized classroom observation tool. This includes, being reflective on where to apply the indicators in every part of the lesson (TR9), by studying and looking for learning competencies that fits the lesson (TR25)

and by continuing to learn and learn of the things that needs to be improved during observation.

Moreover, intensified training and workshop on the use of ICT is another suggestion made by the school administrators to cope with the challenges encountered in using the tool. As for SA19 and SA19, more ICT training will be provided during LAC sessions and off course allow them and teachers to attend trainings in ICT development.

Indeed, teachers are doing their best to cope with the challenges they experienced with the use of standardized classroom observation tool. They may differ in their ways and means but they both aimed to help in planning their teaching-learning process and other phases included in the profession.

Fig 2: Strategies Used by the Teachers’ and School Administrators to Cope with the Challenges they encountered in using the standardized classroom observation tool.

VIII. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study was limited to the teachers’ and school administrators’ perception on the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose and usefulness in teaching and learning process. A total of 30 teachers and 30 school administrators in Sultan Naga Dimaporo served as respondents of the study. Before floating the questionnaire, questionnaire was subjected to face validation. Comments and suggestions made by the panel of experts were accommodated for the betterment of the questionnaire. Then, pilot testing was done, and this was subjected to reliability test using Cronbach Alpha. After revision, it was then implemented to the teachers and school administrators. However, this study was constrained by the time of its implementation.

IX. CONCLUSION

This study sought to determine the differences on the perception of the teachers and school administrators on the use of Standardized Classroom Observation Tool. The study found out that both teachers and school administrators have positive perception in the use of standardized classroom observation tool in terms of clarity of purpose while highly positive perception in terms of its usefulness in teaching and learning process.

With the aim of professional development, both teachers and school administrators agreed that the tool had empower them to reflect on their own teaching and supervising and identify pedagogical needs and initiate innovation for the benefit of the learners. In terms of the clarity of purpose, school administrators and teachers fully understand that the tool guides in the assessment of the teacher’s performance, for it accurately describes teachers expected performance. It

also enhances their skills in the integration of ICT in the teaching and learning process. They also noted that they had a highly positive satisfaction on the use of observation tool in the teaching and learning process.

Generally, although teachers and school administrators have positive perception on the usefulness of the tool in the teaching and learning process, it can be noted that they have different interpretations on the items. However, both negatively perceived on the statement that the classroom observation tool fails to help teachers to grow and improve learners' learning. Thus, in some way they considered the tool as driving force to help teachers grow professionally that will lead to the improvement of learner's learning. Furthermore, teachers and school administrators' perception on the use of standardized classroom observation has no significant difference. This only means that they both perceived the use of the tool similarly.

Moreover, based on the qualitative support of the data gathered, teachers and school administrators identified some challenges they encountered in the use of standardized classroom observation tool. These includes students' ability to understand and have positive engagement in learning, difficulty in achieving objectives and positive learning outcomes, lack of awareness in the indicators, insufficient instructional materials, observer's preferences, preparation, and the nature of the tool. Time management, peer tutoring, giving more technical assistance, constant communication, self-learning, intensive training, and workshop specifically on the use of ICT.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the research findings, the researcher wishes to make the following recommendations:

1. Observers such as school heads may be trained enough to administer the best supervisory observations and advice. Likewise, teachers also may be re-oriented properly to have a clear understanding on the mode of verification.
2. Teachers may also be provided with intensive training on ICT, specifically those who are not computer literate.
3. School administrators must ensure that there is transparency of making judgements based on the performance of the teachers and not on the emotional aspect.
4. Teachers and school administrators may discuss issues about required standards in the performance of duties and be updated on what is required of them by making this as one of the topics during learning action cell sessions and in-service training
5. School administrators may implement and conduct classroom observation following a matrix of schedule so that mentoring may take place where teachers find ways to improve their performance.
6. Training and seminar-workshop on teachers and school administrators focusing on the understanding of the classroom observation tool may be implemented.
7. The future researcher may conduct another study to continue investigating the perceptions of the teachers and school administrators on the use of standardized classroom observation tool using a larger sample of teachers.

➤ Proposed Action Plan

Table 7 Proposed Action Plan

Target Challenge to Take Action	Objective/s	Activities	Persons Involved	Duration	Expected Output
1. Re-orientation on the Standardized classroom observation tool	To help teachers and school administrators be re-oriented with the standardized classroom observation tool to have a uniform understanding on the mode of verification	Re-orientation activity	School administrators and teachers	Quarterly	100% of the teachers and school administrators understand the mode of verification stipulated in the standardized classroom observation tool
2. Intensive training and workshop on integration ICT	To develop mastery in the use of ICT tools in the teaching and learning process.	Training and seminar-workshop	School administrators, teachers, and IT experts	Quarterly	100% of the teachers will be familiar on the use of ICT in teaching and learning process.
3. Re-orientation on the proper evaluation of teachers' performance during classroom observation	To help school administrators give value-laden judgement on the performance of the teachers.	Seminars and trainings	School Administrators	Quarterly	100% of the teachers be able to understand the proper way of giving judgement to the performance of the teacher during classroom observation.

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